

The Policy Performance Evaluation of Tanjung Selor's New Independent City Development, North Kalimantan

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Abstract:

This paper aims to describe and explain the policy performance evaluation of Tanjung Selor's new independent city development. New city development is a systematic process and must pay attention to supporting aspects at all stages of development. A new city development policy is important in solving urban problems and encouraging the level of urban development. The research method used is qualitative, with a descriptive approach. Data collection techniques in this research include literature studies, interviews, and field observations. The factual findings of this research are explained through input, process, output, and outcome indicators. Based on

input indicators, budget, and human resource limitations constrain Tanjung Selor's new independent city development. Then the process indicators regarding the development of Tanjung Selor's new independent city have also not been carried out effectively. While the output indicator is that the ministry's performance is not following prevailing regulations. And finally, on the outcomes indicator, Tanjung Selor's new independent city development is aimed at fulfilling facilities and infrastructure by rejuvenating the old city. In conclusion, the performance of Tanjung Selor's new independent city development policy has not been running as a whole and is still partial, besides that there are still several obstacles that must be improved, especially in terms of budget and human resources.

Keywords: *evaluation, policy performance, new city, development.*

Introduction

Public policies concerning the development of an area include all components of development, as well as all infrastructure in the area (Alamsyah, 2016). Public policy can be said to be successful if it is implemented and has a positive impact on society (Ramdhani 2017). At least, two main

concepts of policy support each other in the development process in Indonesia. First, development is a process of change needed to improve various aspects of people's lives. Second, the implementation of a policy is a form of follow-up activity from the process of formulating and determining a policy. Therefore,

policy implementation can be interpreted as individual or group actions that are oriented toward achieving targets in policy decisions (Basir, Mahsyar, & Parawangi, 2019).

The study of policy evaluation concentrates on specific topics related to outcomes and processes in a policy, e.g. the difference between products and outcomes in the evaluation process (Anderson 2008; Filgueiras and Queiroz 2021). Policy evaluation is an indispensable stage in a policy cycle to assess the implementation of the policy. Three types of policy evaluations can be carried out, namely: a) Ex-ante evaluation, is a policy evaluation carried out before the implementation of a policy. b) Ongoing Evaluation, an evaluation carried out in the process of running the policy. c) Ex-Post evaluation is carried out to assess policy outcomes (Wollman 2007; Lintjewas, et.al 2016).

In many developed countries, the development of new cities is one of the strategies for managing urbanization. new city development is believed and seen as the only way to address the problem of rapid urbanization, while, and without necessarily conflicting with, rural and agricultural land development and conservation. (Heba, Salheen, & Randa, 2015). Following Indonesia's regional development policy, new cities were initially defined as growth and buffer centers within a system of nodal areas. Growth centers are extensions of already overpopulated neighboring cities, which are constrained by urban growth and lack of space, and are therefore unable to provide housing for the growing population (Rustiadi, 2020).

The development of new cities is intended to reduce the burden of large cities, especially in terms of population or people who are increasing so development is needed in relatively new areas to reduce movement in an urban area (Diningrat, 2014). The development and development of new cities can be determined by several factors, including social factors in the form of quality of life and population, land factors in the form of land use patterns and land prices, economic factors in the form of economic business activities and economic political activities, and development

management factors from partnerships and institutions (Batudoka, 2005). The development of new cities is carried out as one of the strategies in the management of increasing urbanization in the region or metropolitan city area so that the use of resources is more optimal and the provision of services to the community becomes more effective and adequate (Siregar, 2012). The development of a new city does not have to be in an empty area or land, but can also be done in a small city that requires further development to become an independent new city.

The emergence of new cities in Indonesia is closely related to urbanization and industrialization, high migration, the development of metropolises and metropolitan areas, degradation of the quality of life and the environment in large cities or metropolises, sporadic and continuous urban development, and efforts to inhibit urbanization and improve the quality of life and the environment (Pratomo, Ayuni, & Fitrianiingsih, 2021). Motivations for developing new cities include urban-rural balance, equitable development, inhibiting urbanization, improving people's lives, solving housing and settlement and transportation problems, and realizing environmentally sustainable development. According to Komarudin (1999), new cities in Indonesia can be divided into independent cities and supporting cities. Independent cities consist of general cities (government centers), company cities (industry, mining, forest businesses), and special cities (military installations, manpower, research and experiment centers, science and technology, recreation centers or resorts, and special settlements). Meanwhile, supporting new cities can be satellite towns or new cities on the outer periphery of large cities (large-scale housing and settlements) and metropolitan new cities (large-scale housing and settlements, but residents work in large cities).

Following Presidential Instruction (*Inpres*) Number 9/018 concerning the Acceleration of the Development of Tanjung Selor New Independent City (abbreviated as KBM), the development of the Tanjung Selor new city area is an effort by the government to support low-income people and as a buffer for urbanization.

Therefore, the development of this New Independent City is an urgent matter and must be implemented. Regarding this, all agencies responsible for the development of the new independent city of Tanjung Selor need to take concrete steps in terms of establishing planning activities to support the development of livable and sustainable residential areas. Tanjung Selor is currently still positioned as a Regional Activity Centre (*Pusat Kegiatan Wilayah*). In future projections, Tanjung Selor as the Provincial Capital must become a National Activity Centre (*Pusat Kegiatan Nasional*) that can synergize with surrounding districts/cities.

In supporting development policies, of course, not only planning is needed, but there is also a need for supervision in the implementation process oriented towards the overall objectives of the government organization (Wijayanto 2020). In the early stages of the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM), to be precise in 2019 the Governor of North Kalimantan in office, projected a budget for the construction of the New Independent City (KBM) around IDR 200-300 billion and is targeted for completion in 2023. However, the development was delayed due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, from mid-2020 until the end of 2021, the construction of the New Independent City (KBM) has been carried out by clearing land and building main roads (CNBC Indonesia, 2019).

Based on this description, this study aims to evaluate by describing the implementation of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) development based on Presidential Instruction (*Impres*) No. 9/2018, as well as analyzing the efforts of the North Kalimantan Provincial Government in implementing strategies to overcome the problems that caused the slow development of the New Independent City in Tanjung Selor.

Materials and Methods

This research is on the implementation of Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) development policy using qualitative methods

and descriptive approaches. Qualitative research is a process for understanding social problems and human problems that are presented scientifically based on a holistic overview (Cresswell, 2016). This research also aims to provide a description or explanation of the facts regarding the performance of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) development policy.

Data collection was conducted through literature studies, observations, and interviews. The literature study was conducted by building a set of theories and used as a basic reference for this research. The literature study that has been carried out is used as a theoretical basis that guides the conduct of this research.

Observations were made by visiting the Tanjung Selor new independent city (KBM) development site. Observations include all locations that are being built into new independent cities (KBM). Interviews were conducted using purposive sampling techniques with selected subjects from the Regional Infrastructure Development Agency (BPIW). Interviews were also conducted using snowball sampling techniques with eight people in Tanjung Selor's new independent city (KBM) development site.

Primary and secondary data categories were also used in this research. Primary data was obtained through observations and interviews conducted directly at the Regional Infrastructure Development Agency (BPIW), and secondary data was obtained through various documents closely related to the Tanjung Selor new independent city (KBM) development policy process.

Data analysis was carried out through three steps, namely data condensation, data display, and data verification (conclusions). Data condensation is the process of selecting or simplifying the data obtained for subsequent data presentation. Data display refers to data that has been summarized to verify or make conclusions on the data obtained as well as being the final process of data analysis (Miles et al., 2014).

Results

New City development is a systematic process and must consider supporting aspects at the development stage. The development of independent cities outside the main city is expected to maximize the effectiveness of resource utilization (Adisasmita, 2010). New city development policies are important in solving urban problems and encouraging the level of urban development (Cai, De Meulder, Lin, & Sun, 2020). According to Wikantyo (2001), land use regulation to achieve independence in balance requires the concept of a mix used between residential functions, trade, green office, and other functions. The balance of land use allows the balance of socio-economic activities of the community by minimizing movement to and from the main city. Independence in balance in new city planning makes it clear that the development of a new city is not to accommodate a community of people in one social class or one function, but requires

social heterogeneity and functions like the main town community. Its occupational structure and housing composition should cater to a mix of socio-economic groups and economic activities. In general, therefore, the new city should be seen as the development of a variety of functional units not only for housing and commercial facilities but also for employment, education, recreation, health, and other facilities.

Tanjung Selor as the capital of North Kalimantan Province, which is the youngest province in Indonesia, is a city that is prioritized for development in Presidential Regulation No. 2/2015 regarding the National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJM) 2015-2019. The location of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City development is geographically strategically positioned and supported by the *Tanah Kuning* International Port Industrial Estate (KIPI) development project, the Indonesia - Malaysia Border Area in Nunukan and Malinau, and other supporting infrastructure.

Figure 1. Masterplan of Tanjung Selor New Independent City Development

Source: <https://temanalumni.lan.go.id/>

On the other hand, policy performance can support leaders in the public sector in evaluating priority programs and building capacity for

decision-making (Tulloch, 2021). Policy performance can also be used as an assessment of a policy by looking at the output, outcome,

and impact sides (Khandaker, 2021). Assessment of policy performance evaluation is generally carried out based on four main indicators, namely: input, process, output, and outcomes indicators (Bridgman & Davis 2000).

In the development of Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM), there are quite several aspects that affect the development policy, causing it not to meet the target. Therefore, as stated (Badjuri & Yuwono, 2002) policy evaluation needs to be carried out on the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) by referring to four indicators, namely: inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes. And based on the type of ongoing evaluation policy evaluation considering that the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) development policy is

still in the implementation stage, following Presidential Instruction (*Inpres*) No. 9/2018.

Input Indicators

The first indicator used by researchers in carrying out policy evaluation is the input indicator. Based on this indicator, the North Kalimantan Regional Development Infrastructure Division (BPPW) said three aspects supported the implementation of the Tanjung Selor Independent New City development, namely:

1) Regulatory Aspects, Presidential Instruction (*Inpres*) No.9/2018 related to the Acceleration of Tanjung Selor New Independent City Development

Figure 2. Synergy of New City Development in Indonesia

Source: <https://simantu.pu.go.id/content/?id=837>

2) Human Resources (HR) Aspects, Human Resources in Independent New City Development have been supported by parties appointed through Presidential Instruction (*Inpres*) No.9/2018 related to the Acceleration of Tanjung Selor Independent New City

Development, consisting of 12 Ministries / Institutions, North Kalimantan Provincial Government and Bulungan Regency Government.

3) Budgetary Aspects, the Tanjung Selor New Independent City Development Project is

contained in the National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) 2020-2024, so the financing of the development of the New Independent City is budgeted through the State Budget (APBN) and supported through Regional Government Budget (APBD) funding by its authority.

Furthermore, regarding the amount of budget and human resources needed in the development of the New Independent City in Tanjung Selor, the North Kalimantan Regional Development Infrastructure Division (BPPW) has not been able to estimate the budget needed, but considering that the development of the New Independent City starts from zero, the amount of budget needed will be very large. The budget is the main aspect of the government as a supporter in the implementation of all policies (Sulthoni, 2017). Then Human Resources is an important instrument that can increase the success of a policy, and the availability of sufficient human resources will optimize the implementation of a policy (Agustina and Megawati 2022).

Since 2015, National Development Planning Agency (Bappenas) has developed a Roadmap for the Implementation of New City Development Activities in Indonesia. In the New City Development Roadmap prepared by Bappenas, it is clear that the parties are involved, both Ministries and Institutions at the National level and Local Governments. The involvement of related parties is continuous from the planning, development, and operational management stages. New City Development fundamentally emphasizes the principle of integration of all relevant parties in all stages of sustainable urban development (preparation, planning, development, operation, and management). Cross-sectoral and inter-level institutional involvement (Marpaung, 2018).

Process Indicators

The process indicators describe the methods applied and the level of efficiency of the methods applied, and in this process indicator, the researcher applies SWOT analysis which is intended to be more detailed in analysis. Then regarding the extent to which the development

of the New Independent City (KBM) has been carried out, based on the results of interviews with the North Kalimantan Regional Development Infrastructure Division (BPPW), the method or method applied which is then transformed into the form of implementing the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) has been outlined in the Masterplan and Development Plan prepared by the Regional Infrastructure Development Agency (BPIW) of the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR) in 2019, which serves as a guideline in the division of tasks for the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) by the functions of each ministry agency, provincial government and district government.

As a form of initial steps in the development of Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM), the government has set four initial steps in the development of the New Independent City in Tanjung Selor, first, revising Regional Regulation (Perda) No. 4/2013 related to the Regional Spatial Plan (RTRW) in Bulungan Regency (declared no longer valid), second, preparing an effective and efficient Tanjung Selor development plan, third, preparing physical infrastructure as a support for the development and preparing Human Resources as a form of planning that can support the development of the city of Tanjung Selor; fourth, by compiling a Work Plan (Renja) for the development of the New Independent City in Tanjung Selor. Based on the SWOT analysis technique, the following are the results of the analysis of the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM).

Based on Table 1, it is known that the strengths that can support the implementation of the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) are regulations, considering that in the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM), two regulations form the basis for the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM), namely Presidential Instruction No. 9/2018 concerning the acceleration of the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City and Presidential

Regulation (*Perpres*) No. 18/2020 concerning the National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) 2020-2024 period. As for the weaknesses, namely the low fiscal capacity of the central government and the North Kalimantan provincial government, then there is a tug of war in financing the land maturation of the New Independent City (KBM) development area and the less effective role of the ministry in focusing

activities and providing budgets. This is because in 2020 the government implemented a refocusing policy intended to deal with the covid-19 pandemic so that the budget that had originally been designed for the development of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) was diverted to handling covid-19.

Table 1. SWOT analysis of Tanjung Selor New Independent City Development

<p>Strength:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulation - Planning Documents - Land Availability 	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for priority activity programs carried out by the national government - Assistance from the private sector in the form of cooperation with the government
<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low fiscal capacity of the central and provincial governments - Tug-of-war in financing the land development of the government center area between the central government and the provincial government - The less effective role of ministries in budget implementation and delivery 	<p>Threats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changing global, national, and regional economic conditions - National political regime change that does not support the development of new cities

Source: Research Finding, 2022

While external factors, which can provide opportunities for the development of Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) are the support of priority activity programs by the central government and assistance from the private sector in the form of cooperation with the government. Those that can have a negative effect on the development of this New Independent City (KBM) are unstable economic conditions in the global, national, and regional sectors. And the change of national political regime that does not favor the development of new cities.

Then, based on the results of interviews with the North Kalimantan Regional Development Infrastructure Division (BPPW), in the

implementation of the development of the New Independent City (KBM), two parties play a role, namely the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR) and the North Kalimantan provincial government, until now the two parties have not built enough supporting infrastructure to support the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM).

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the progress of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) development has been partly carried out, especially in the construction of supporting infrastructure which will later function as a support in the operation of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City.

Table 2. Supporting Infrastructure Progress of Tanjung Selor New Independent City Development

Level of Government	Supporting Infrastructure Progress
Ministry of Public Works and Housing (PUPR)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Construction of 250 liters/second <i>Kayan</i> River intake 2) Partial construction process of <i>Kayan</i> River intake transmission pipeline 3) Construction of <i>Gunung Seriang</i> Water Management Installation (IPA) 4) Partial construction process of government center access road
Provincial Government of North Kalimantan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Land acquisition for the government center area of 590 Ha 2) Partial construction process of the outer ring road 3) Partial construction process of the Office Building of the Provincial House of Representatives (DPRD). North Kalimantan and Vertical Agencies 4) Partial construction process of Government Office Building 1 unit

Source: Research Finding, 2022

Output Indicator

The intended output indicator is to find out the Tanjung Selor New Independent City development policy. Based on the results of interviews with the North Kalimantan Regional Development Infrastructure Division (BPPW), the development of the New Independent City (KBM) is intended to provide a New City that is organized by the planning process (which does not grow organically / scientifically) on undeveloped land or rural areas, which has sufficient readiness of population, socio-cultural and economic aspects, and has adequate facilities and infrastructure, to support a sustainable future city. This is under the concept of New Independent City (KBM) development which is expected to provide a multiplier effect in various sectors with a sustainable form of development.

Furthermore, the input indicator is intended to determine the parties that have been involved in the development of Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM), through the results of the interview it is known that so far there are a total of nine parties who have carried out tasks in the implementation of the development of Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM), namely; (1) Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs, (2) Coordinating Ministry for Maritime Affairs and Investment, (3) Ministry of National Development Planning (*Bappenas*), (4) Ministry of Public Works and Housing, (5) Ministry of

Transportation, (6) Ministry of Agrarian Affairs and Spatial Planning, (7) Ministry of Communication and Information, (8) Provincial Government of North Kalimantan and (9) Local Government of Bulungan. Based on this, there has been a discrepancy in the implementation of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) development policy, it is known that Presidential Instruction No. 9 of 2018 which is listed in the action plan for the development of the New Independent City (KBM) has been signed by 12 related parties, but in its implementation only nine parties have implemented the policy.

Seeing this, it can be understood that in the implementation of the Tanjung Selor New Independent City (KBM) development policy, there is no integration between actors and good coordination implementing the policy. The integration of actors needs to be done to glue and synergize activities between actors so that their implementation becomes more effective and efficient (Ferry, 2020). Then regarding the success and effectiveness of a policy, it will be determined by the role of actors who are coordinated in the implementation and control processes in policy implementation (Iskandar 2018).

Outcomes Indicator

The outcomes indicator intended in this study is intended to determine the impact that will be felt

by the wider community or parties involved in the development of the New Independent City (KBM), from the results of interviews with the North Kalimantan Regional Infrastructure Development Agency (BPIW), it is known that in the development of the New Independent City (KBM), the impact that can be felt is the creation of the fulfillment of basic facilities and infrastructure through the rejuvenation of the old city (outside the central government area) of Tanjung Selor.

However, the development of the New Independent City (KBM) also has a negative impact, because in a new area development, there will be land use change at the development site, such as reduced water catchment areas and closed water flow paths. Furthermore, in the evaluation of the New Independent City development policy in Tanjung. Based on the results of interviews with the North Kalimantan Regional Development Infrastructure Division (BPPW), it is said that the provincial government of North Kalimantan continues to optimize funding through cooperation with business entities and other possible sources of funds. And in seeking to keep the development of the New Independent City (KBM) running, the Provincial Government of North Kalimantan will continue to develop basic infrastructure in the central government area, then regarding the validity period of the Presidential Instruction which will expires the Governor of North Kalimantan will submit a request regarding the letter of extension of the validity period of the Presidential Instruction. The form of cooperation between the government and the private sector/business entity is possible to be implemented in the provision of government budget in infrastructure development. Partnership activities are important for the government to carry out with the private sector to increase the amount of budget for infrastructure provision (Setiawan & Warsa, 2018).

Discussion

The main idea of new cities is to form a development plan within a certain period of time, to achieve a balance, the needs of

population facilities, determine the limits of growth in addition to connecting different land use functions and improving the quality of life of the community (Campbell 1976). In addition, new cities can also be understood as land development projects that can provide complete and intact urban elements, which include housing, social facilities, trade, and industry, which as a whole can provide: opportunities to live in the neighborhood, a variety of housing types and prices, active and passive open spaces and buffer zones, as well as physical environment control programs and activities (Sujarto, 2005).

New cities are also characterized by a new lifestyle concept: living in a green and healthy environment. New cities are the answer to divert cities that are already overcrowded and congested to new locations in the form of new cities. The development of new cities has served as a relocation for overcrowded cities. It should not be forgotten that new cities also exploit rural land that may have been used for other land use development such as for agricultural land or recreational and nature areas (Thorgeirsdottir, 2010). Thus, new cities have been interpreted as housing relocations for overcrowded cities or suburban living areas that are safe for families (Reijndorp, 2006).

New city development in its development should be a cornerstone in conceptual thinking for solving urban problems, such as urban congestion and community settlement arrangements in various countries around the world, including, Indonesia (Agustina, 2007). The development of new cities has a significant impact on providing planned settlements, providing more adequate infrastructure that reduces dependence on larger cities and communities will be able to carry out activities and effectively utilize resources and related elements (Diningrat, 2014). In addition, dependency on new cities is usually a great opportunity to occur because the new city area is still dependent on the surrounding main city or big city because it has a greater attraction and promise so development by strategic objectives and careful planning is needed (Diningrat, 2014).

In addition, the development of new cities in the future must prioritize the concept of green city. Green city as a concept in sustainable city development must adapt to the environment, namely the environment created by humans as a form of response to environmental damage that has occurred with the existing natural environment (Ratnasari, Sitorus, & Tjahjono, 2015). As for Irsan Ely Kibas. et. al. (2023) argue about the concept of a green city as a concept in urban development by considering environmental aspects based on participatory and ecology (Kibas, Surya, Jufriadi, & Anggraini, 2023). In the green city, it is mentioned that the natural environment is used for the benefit of urban residents (Saraswati, Kusmayanti, Darmawan, Adhi, Rini, & Anindyajati, 2021).

The concept of a green city, which is based on the principle of sustainable development, must be able to create an environmentally friendly city by optimizing the natural and artificial environment, optimizing the use of energy and water resources, improving environmental health, and reducing the amount of waste (Ernawi, 2012). Therefore, green open space is needed as an important part of a green city that functions as an oxygen provider, carbon dioxide absorber, and water storage to support urban resilience (Fuady, 2021). The green city was created due to the background of the rapid growth in urban areas with implications for the emergence of problems or issues that occur, such as flooding, lack of green open space, slums, urban congestion, and social disparities between communities (Anugerah, Sujianto, & Adlin, 2016).

Urban development in the green city concept must have a balanced ecosystem so that the benefits can be felt sustainably (Wildsmith, 2009). Realizing an effective and efficient green city requires 8 attributes according to the Green City Development Program (P2KH), namely the design and planning of an environmentally friendly city (green design and planning), management and utilization of waste using the 3R principle (green waste), the use of a sustainable transportation system (green transportation), the availability of green open space (green open space), the increased role of

the community as a green community, efficient use of energy resources (green energy), use of energy-efficient buildings or buildings (green building), and effective management and use of water (green water) to consider the impact on the environment (Mugni, Azis, Yahya, 2021). Green cities do not only sacrifice or use the assets of a city, but also nurture and enhance the available assets, such as the natural environment, people, and infrastructure (Prasetya et.al., 2017).

In addition to applying the concept of a green city, the new city built must also be integrated into a smart city. The smart city is the right step in advancing a city in a country based on information and communication technology to form a city that is safe, comfortable, and has strong competitiveness in the economy and makes it easier for people to get information precisely and quickly (Hasibuan & Sulaiman, 2019). In the application of smart cities, each dimension must be interconnected and collaborate, such as in the elements of smart living, smart governance, smart economy, smart environment, smart branding, smart society, and smart economy so that the services provided to the community can be carried out efficiently, effectively, quickly, and precisely (Nurzaman, Rompis, Nurmallasari, & Zulfiani, 2023). Thus, the implementation of smart cities that use information and communication technology will create a smart society through the availability of interactive and effective infrastructure and utilities (Azkuna, 2012). In addition, smart cities aim to create good governance that can provide satisfaction and the needs of the community through technology services (Alawiah, 2017).

Concerning the development of new cities in North Kalimantan, some aspects must still be considered by the North Kalimantan Provincial government. In addition to its direct border with other countries, the majority of the land area of North Kalimantan Province is very steep. North Kalimantan Province is dominated by areas with altitude classes between 100-1,000 m above sea level and very steep. The land area of North Kalimantan Province consists of 38.76 percent at an altitude of 500-1,000 m above sea level and 20.51 percent at an altitude of 100-500 m above sea level. Malinau District has 58.46 percent of

its area at an altitude of 500-1,000m. Meanwhile, Tarakan City is entirely located at an altitude below 25 m above sea level. The 76.72 percent of North Kalimantan Province is an area with a slope of more than 40 percent or categorized as very steep-rugged. Only Tarakan City does not have an area with a slope level above 40 percent.

Although the majority of the land area is very steep, the North Kalimantan region has enormous potential for water resources. These resources consist of a fairly high amount of rainfall, large rivers, many springs, and extensive swamps. Because the area is passed by the equator, the average rainfall in 2020 was 250.86 mm. In addition, North Kalimantan Province is also passed by four major rivers, namely the Kayan River, Bahau River, Sembakung River, and Sesayap River. Kayan River is one of the major rivers in North Kalimantan.

The current development of the new Tanjung Selor independent city is structuring transportation, especially in terms of road networks to support all activities carried out by the people of Tanjung Selor City and increasing accessibility between regions to make it easier and more affordable with the construction of a ring road network in the city of Tanjung Selor which is accompanied by the development of Land Use (*Tata Guna Lahan*) including the Industrial zone, Airport development, development of Sub Terminal-1 Transit Oriented Development (TOD), development of Theme Park-1 Tourism zone (Cultural Centre), development of Hotel and Restaurant zone, Regency / City Government Centre and Provincial Government zone, High Income Residential zone, development of Theme Park-2 Tourism zone (City Square), Sub Terminal-2 Transit Oriented Development (TOD) zone and infrastructure development including road networks that can illustrate the success of development, especially quality economic development.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and the description above, it can be concluded that in the

development of Tanjung Selor Independent New City, the performance of policies in the scope of North Kalimantan province has not carried out its duties as in the established development guidelines. Some of the obstacles are related to the capacity of Human Resources and budget limitations. Regarding this budget constraint, there are quite a lot of influencing factors, both the refocusing policy for handling covid-19 and the performance of the ministry in providing the budget, which has hampered the development of the Tanjung Selor Independent New City (KBM). In addition, a factor that hampers implementation is the role of ministries that are not effective in focusing their activity programs.

As a recommendation, some of the things that the North Kalimantan provincial government still has to do include: optimizing basic infrastructure development in the central government area through partnerships between the government and private parties or state companies. Partnership efforts with the private sector or state companies are choices that can be made so that they do not only depend on financing from the central government. This is so that the development of the New Independent City (KBM) can continue until the new city is developed.

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